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The Jaina Concept of *Dharma*

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Introduction:

Dhamma or *dharma* is a complex term. It contains diverse elements and presents a complex structure. It has been used in a variety of meanings in the *Prākṛta* Jain philosophical literature. Nature of a thing, the essential qualities of an object, element and the moral law are some of the significations in which the term 'dharma' has been employed. Thus owing to the ambiguity of the term 'dharma', it is very difficult to give a precise answer to the question, — what is *dharma*? and what is the relation between the *dharma* and morality?

Dharma includes both philosophy and religion, theory and practice of good life, ascetic culture and ethical behaviour. Merit (*punya*) is not the highest aim of *dharma*; liberation of the soul from the worldly bondage is the ultimate aim of religious culture. *Dharma* is that which takes one to the cherished goal of liberation (*iṣṭesthānedhatteitidharman*)¹.

Dharma in Jainism

Throughout the history of Jain religious and Philosophic thought the vital concept of dharma has been subject to extensive elaboration and on a plurality of meanings². *Dhamma* or *dharma* in Jainism has mainly two levels of meaning: one is technical and specific to the term and the other is generic and broad. In this paper I am trying to concentrate on the explication of the different related denotations of the word *dharma*.

There are varieties meaning of the word dharma in *Prākṛta* and Jain philosophical literature, some of which we have not discussed in this article. Vincent Sekhar³ summarizes the different characteristics of dharma as seen by the Jaina culture in the following way:

1. A system of belief regarding the truth about reality expressed in the Jaina fundamental principles.
2. A vision of great Jaina Ideals of right faith, right knowledge and right conduct.
3. An attitude of pluralism seen as *anekānta*.
4. An ethical precept especially ahimsa and respect for life.
5. A ladder for spiritual formation.
6. A systems of discipline, the ascetic and the householder way of life.
7. And finally as a system of religion, dharma pervades the whole gamut of topics such as the *Tīrthaṅkaras*, *pañcaparameṣṭhis*, worship and spiritual exercises etc. and the authoritative teachings of the *Tīrthaṅkaras* in the holy *Āgamas* (sacred texts).

We may discuss only three different meanings of *Dharma* used in the Jain literature.

(A) *Dhamma* as the Jaina teaching as a whole (*Jinvāṇi*):

From the beginning of the early canonical period, as evidenced by in the *Ācārāṅgasūtra* and *Sutrakṛtāṅgasūtra*, the term *dharma* has been employed as a designation for the Jaina teaching as a whole⁴. This denotation identifies *dharma* with *Jina-Vāṇi*. From the earliest *Āgama* texts onward, the word *dhamma* has been used to indicate the Jain teaching in general. This is in fact appears to be the most frequent use of the term. According to *Uttarādhyāyanasūtra*, the definition of *dhamma* is, belief in the word of the Jina-s or in the law propounded by the *Jina-s*⁵. *Dhamma* has been well taught by the *Jina-s* for the benefit of the world of beings. Those who are devoted

to its practice they can easily cross over the ocean of existence-influx⁶.

Ācāryya Hemacandra in his *Yogaśāstra* cleared this meaning of *dharma* in this sense as:

“svākhyātahkhaludharmo’yambhagavadbhirjinottamaih/
yamsamālabamāno hi namajjedbhavasāgare//92//”

That is to say, ‘the eminent Jinās, who are venerable, have convincingly proclaimed the *dharma* (or Jina’s preaching) which, if understood correctly, saves one from drowning in the ocean of transmigration⁸.

The *dharma* is the kinsman to those without kinsmen, the companion of those without companions, the protector of those without protection. It is indeed the only affectionate one of the whole world⁹. The *dhamma* is the means of attaining all the good things and all kinds of happiness. *Dharma* is the source of good of human life, it even results in the bliss of liberation. In short, the *dharma* taught by the Jina-s destroyer of all sufferings¹⁰.

(B) *Dharma* as Media of Motion:

The second of these denotations identifies *dharma* with a very specific and technical term that is ‘media of motion’. During the late canonical period, a conception of the word *dharma* apparently unique to Jainism is confirmed in *Uttarādhyāyaṇa Sūtra*¹¹(XXVIII. 7-9, 14, XXXVI.5). The word *dharma* and its opposite *adharmā* were equated, in the Āgama texts, with two of the six ontological categories (*dravyas*) — medium of movement (*dharma-dravya*) and medium of rest (*adharmā-dravya*). These two *dravyas* were said to create the conditions and support for activity and non-activity respectively¹². *Tattvārtha Sūtra* says : ‘*gati-sthityupagraho dharmā-adharmayorupakārah*¹³’ i.e., the function of the medium of motion is to act as the supporting cause for motion and the function of the medium of rest is to act as the supporting cause for rest¹⁴.

Dharma in this specific ontological usage is the basis for movement or motion as it is opposed to *adharmā* or stillness or rest. *Dharma* and *adharmā* are said to occupy the whole inhabited space of the universe (*Lokākāśa*). *Dharma* functions to support the movement of *Jīva* (the Self), the principle of life, and the *puḍgala*, matter, while *adharmā* works as the medium of bringing them to rest. In other words, *Jīva* and *puḍgala* can move and stop by their own nature, but only with the help of *dharma* and *adharmā*¹⁵.

While life and matter are both capable of moving of their own accord determined by appropriate operative causal conditions, their movement is dependent upon the presence of the non-operative principle called *dharma*. Remaining in itself non-operative, *dharma* serves as a condition for making movement possible. Nathamal Tatia explains the medium of motion is the supporting cause. Without it motion is impossible¹⁶. We may explain the nature of *dharma* with some general illustration. Puḍyapāda Devanandi in his commentary *Sarvārtha Siddhi* illustrates the functions of medium of motion by likening it to the water through which a fish swims¹⁷. When a fish swims, the movement is due to an imperative cause. Just as water helps the fish to move about, even so *dharma* makes the movement of soul and matter possible.

Dharma is imperceptible, though it fills the entire universe, life and matter. It has none of the characteristic qualities of life or matter, but forms the medium of motion, which is possible only through its existence. It has three divisions — *skandha* (whole), *deśa* (part) and *pradeśa* (portion of a part) and as a condition of motion it is pervasive. *Dharma* here should not be confused with righteousness¹⁸.

Here a question may arise: why is *dharma* is needed as a separate ontological category? We may respond to this question following the *Tattvārtha Sūtra*¹⁹ of Ācāryya Umasvāti as: though the *dharma* and *adharmā* concern all movements and rest of *Jīva* and *puḍgala*, their main function seems to help a liberated *Jīva* move up to the top

of the universe and stay there²⁰. This suggests a new and different understanding of *dharma* and *adharma*, which is unique to Indian Philosophy.

(C) *Dharma* as Morality:

The third and general usage of the term *Dharma* is purely ethical or moral. For Jainism, *Dharma* serves to underscore the need to observe correct and auspicious behaviours and is often understood as religion or moral code. In Jaina philosophy metaphysics and ethics are the two sides of the same coin. There could not have been a better proof of the realisation of this relation between metaphysics and ethics than the employment of the word *dhamma* for the 'essential nature of things' (*vaṣṭusvabhāvaḥ*) on the one hand, and for 'moral duties' on the other²¹. According to Jainism, right faith precedes right conduct²². No conduct or knowledge without right faith can be said to be right²³. The *Pravacanasāra* says:

“Cārīttvamkhaludhammo, dhammojo so samottinidittho/
Mohakkhahovihinoparināmoappanohusamo//²⁴

Conduct is *Dharma*, *dharma* is equanimity (*sāmya*), and equanimity means that condition of *atman* which is free from delusion and agitation²⁵. According to Jaina scripture *Dasaveyaliya* or *Daśavaikālika Sūtra*, 'dhammomangalomukkhithaṅgahimsāsanj-*amotabo*', that is to say, *Dhamma* is made up of 'non-violence', 'self-control' and 'austerity'²⁶. And in this reason, it is argued that, *dharma* is difficult to comprehend; and therefore, even though violence is otherwise bad, when sanctioned by religion, violence is no sin²⁷. In *Mokṣa-Pāhuḍa*, *Ācāryya* Kundakunda defines *samyagdarśana* as belief in *dharma* or religion as devoid of violence, in the way of life as prescribed by the omniscient²⁸. *Ācāryya* Hemacandra in his *Yogaśāstra* cleared this consequence of fostering *dharma* in this way:

“*dharma*prabhāvatahkalpadrumādyādadatipsitam”²⁹

Again, “*Dharmonarakapātālapātādavatidehinah/
dharmonirupamamyacchatyapisarvajnavaihbavam*//³⁰”

That is to say, 'due to the impact of *Dharma*, which is similar to a wish-fulfilling tree, all desires are fulfilled'. '*dharma* alone protects the self from falling into the pits of fell. *Dharma* alone bestows the incomparable wealth of omniscience'.

Amṛtacandra states:

“*svarupeccaranamcārītramsvasamayapravrttityarthah/
Tadevavastusvabhāvatvāddharmah/
Suddhacaitanyaprakāsanamityarthah*”³¹

i.e., 'conduct is behaving according to one's nature; activity obeying one's (innate) laws. And this from being the nature of things is *dharma* (duty); it means the manifestation of pure intelligence'³².

Mūlācāra says that a Jain monk should cultivate ten cardinal virtues in himself³³. Those are called *daśadharmas*³⁴. The practicing of these *dharma* helps to control our senses and sleep³⁵. Those ten *dharmas*, according to Hemacandra, are :

*Samyamahsānṛtamsaucambrahmākīñcanatātapah/
kṣāntirmārdavamrjūtāmuktiscadasadhāsatu*³⁶/

i.e., this *dharma* is tenfold, consisting of restraint, truthfulness, purity, continence, non-attachment, austerity, forbearance, modesty, uprightness and renunciation.

These ten *dharmas* have been enumerated in Sutra 6 of Chapter IX of the *Tattvārtha Sūtra* as follows:

“*Uttamakṣamamārdavārjivasatyāśaucasāmyamatapastyāga
akīñcanyabrahmacaryanidharmah*.”³⁷

Supreme forbearance, humility, straightforwardness, truthfulness, purity, self-control, austerity, renunciation, non-attachment and celibacy constitute the religion or *dharma*. These ten *dharmas* are intended to regulate the activities of mind, thought and action. Their practice or observance gives direction to the life of a votary by eliminating all his evil thoughts and preventing him from harmful

actions. The word *uttama* or supreme ought to be read along with each of the *dharmas* implying thereby that the practice should be of the highest order or in full measure. There should be no expectation of any earthy reward except that of attaining purity and spiritual advancement. It is appropriate to discuss them in the order in which they are enumerated above.

1) *Uttama Kṣamā* or Supreme Forbearance

Supreme forbearance or forgiveness is a divine virtue. It is the most powerful armour of man. There is nothing like the maxim '*forget and forgive*'. The spirit of forgiveness helps a great way to control anger which eats into the moral vitals of the *mumukṣin*³⁸. T. K. Tukul, when he explain this dharma says that : for an ascetic, there might situations when he is abused; insulted or rebuked by people who are opposed to his way of life. He must bear everything calmly and think within himself that all such display of temper is due to ignorance of the importance of the codes of saintly life and that he should forgive all those who might be prone to cause him mental or physical pain³⁹.

2) *Uttama Mārdava* or Supreme Humility

Mārdava or softness means humility in word and deed; it brings in freedom from self-conceit and makes man kind in his heart and humble in his disposition. Modesty is born of true education and culture. Pride or self-conceit is the greatest enemy of true knowledge, faith and understanding⁴⁰. Humility arises when pride about one's race, family, property, intellect, knowledge and other such attainments, is subdued. The *Svopajña Bhāṣya* of *Tattvārtha Sūtra* describes humility as lack of self-aggrandizement and control and destruction of pride⁴¹. It destroys all misconception and wrong knowledge while creating a thirst for acquisition of right knowledge or conduct.

3) *Uttama Ārjava* or Supreme straightforwardness

Straightforwardness is sincere and honest intention. Every honest man is consistent in his thoughts, words and deeds while the reverse is the case with a bad person. To be straight-forward is to be

free from cunning, duplicity, ambiguity and evasiveness in thoughts, words and deeds. "By simplicity he will become upright in actions, thoughts and speech and he will become veracious; and thereby he will practice the law" says *Bhagavāna Mahāvira*⁴².

Straightforwardness conduces to clarity of intellect and purity of thought. It leads to honesty of purpose of thought and action. The mind of such a person will always be peaceful⁴³.

4) *Uttama Satya* or Perfect Truthfulness

"Truthfulness" includes refraining from harsh words, back-biting, garrulity, derogatory language, vituperation and so on. Truthfulness has been discussed with utmost importance under the title of five *vratas* recommended for monk and lay person. The fact that it is again included in the category of ten noble virtues only indicates that Jainism attaches very great importance to it as its practice in everyday life is the key to purity of life.

The *Uttarādhyāyana Sūtras* peaks of *bhāva-satya*, *Kāraṇa-satya* and *Yoga-satya* which respectively mean sincerity of mind, sincerity of religious practices and sincerity of action⁴⁴. Sincerity of thought or truthfulness purifies the mind and helps the individual fully in the practice of religion: sincere practice of religion frees the individual from accumulated Karmas and stops the influx of new ones.

5) *Uttama Śauca* or Supreme Purity

Purity means to be free of greed. Purity cleanses the mind from craving and greed and produces contentment and equanimity. Purity or cleanliness of external body without the corresponding internal purity serves no purpose. The *Svopajña Bhāṣya* of *Tattvārtha Sūtra* describes that internal purity is often obscured by anger, greed, pride, deceit, violence and falsehood. Real purity of the soul consists in getting rid of all these weaknesses which are the sources of all misery in the world.

Perfect faith and knowledge are essential for the purity of mind and thought. Without them, the cravings of existence, of the senses, of the body and of enjoyment are likely to mislead us from the right path. Purity cannot be achieved unless these are controlled and subdued.

6) *Uttama Samiyama* or Perfect Self-restraint

Self-restraint refers to abstaining from all activities which injure any form of life, subtle or gross. Restraint in thoughts, speech and action is self-restraint; that is the basis of pure life and religion. It is difficult to attain self-restraint. The *Svopajña Bhāṣya* of *Tattvārtha Sūtra* identifies controlling body, speech and mind and in particular, carefully inspecting objects and places so as to avoid injuring life.

7) *Uttama Tapas* or Supreme Austerity

Practice of penance is order to destroy the accumulated *Karmas* is austerity. External austerities are of twelve kinds while the internal austerities are of six kinds. According to *Umāsvāti*, the external austerities are fasting, reduction of diet, restrictions on begging food, abstinence from delicious and stimulating foods or dishes, lonely habitation and mortification of the body⁴⁵. Austerity means mortification of the body for the regeneration of the soul. Observance of austerity is the stepping stone to attainment of spiritual strength or greatness. One has to withdraw oneself from a life of sensual pleasures and achieve detachment from the lure of material possessions. Jainism attaches the greatest importance to penance. It is by penance that one destroys the accumulated *Karmas* and obtains purity of mind and thought⁴⁶.

8) *Uttama Tyāga* or Complete renunciation

Renunciation is the abandonment of positive attitudes towards the necessities of life. It is a difficult virtue in practice. The first stage of cultivating this virtue is to possess a strong determination against acquisition. The second step is that of renunciation by making

donations and gifts to good causes. *Aparigraha* or non-possessiveness which is one of the five *vratas* would apply with equal appropriateness to the subject of renunciation.

9) *Uttama Ākiñcanya* or Complete Non-attachment

He who has nothing is *akiñcana*. To entertain such a thought is *ākiñcanya*. In this world, there is nothing that one can legitimately call his own. Even the body is not his own, as it is independent of the soul. The object of this virtue is that everyone should firmly know as a matter of faith and ultimate reality that the *ātman* has nothing that he can call his own, the body, the relatives, the family etc. belong to the body and that it is only by cherishing such ideas that he can achieve the noble goal of life. *Ākiñcanya*, if gradually developed in the mind and practiced, is the surest path to asceticism of the highest order.

10) *Uttama Brahmacharya* or Supreme Celibacy

Constant awareness of the *Ātman* or *Brahman* without being distracted by sensual pleasures is *Brahmacharya*. Physical passion destroys the stability of mind. Passion of any kind is dangerous to spiritual progress. The monk, being celibate, should be absolutely free from any type of sexual desire. According to *Tattvārtha Sūtra*, to keep up their celibacy, the monk should avoid certain things such as (a) looking at the women, (b) Recalling past sexual enjoyment (c) stories relating to attachment to women, (d) rich delicious food, (e) decoration of the body⁴⁷. In fact, celibacy is helpful for concentration of spiritual activities. It purifies the mind, strengthens the intellect and leads one to a higher concentration.

Dharma and Morality: Moral Significance of Jain Dharma:

These ten noble *dharmas* form part of Jaina morality and ethics. It is often said that *dharmas* has its own reward or intrinsic values. An individual who has acquires these *dharmas* gets his reward in the form of spiritual advancement of his own soul. He is freed from ignorance and passions and achieves firmness in Right Faith and

conquers all wickedness. All these *dharmas* are inherent characteristics of every soul⁴⁸. What is inherent has to be understood and realized.

Every religion is a motivating and guiding force to people, who profess that religion. Every religion professes a value system that has an impact on the wider society. What are common in Jain religion is to help everyone to have a meaningful relationship to one another.

In Jaina ethics, morality, whether it is individualistic or altruistic, is only a practical way of speaking (*vyāvahārika*). Worldly happiness achieved for oneself or for the other is not the ultimate end of morality. The ultimate aim of morality is to uproot even the subtlest form of passions. Therefore the relative life of virtue and vice is to be abandoned in favour of life of pure consciousness⁴⁹. *Munidharma* or *Śrāvaka-dharma* (ascetic and lay ethics) are the representatives of the two levels of morality. *Munidharma* is sometimes understood as individual ethics and that of the laity is called social ethics⁵⁰. Jaina dharma upholds the individual's efforts in conquering passions and activities, it also understands and accepts the relevance of social duties and responsibilities like helping others etc. apparently it seems that Jaina ethics lay more emphasis on individual efforts and on ascetic virtues but finally and practically it gives emphasis on social and positive virtues⁵¹. Because observance of individual rules of conduct, ultimately took the responsibility to purify the moral character of the whole society.

Evaluation:

Distinguished Jaina scholar Nathmal Tatia says, 'Jainism has a system of ethics that places *ahimsā* and *anekānta* at the top of its principles of morality'⁵². The compassion (*anukampā*) of Mahāvīra is a many-faceted virtue. It is abstinence from causing suffering to any living thing, on the one hand, and the positive act of rendering service to others for eradicating their suffering, on the other hand.

This is the implication of *Tattvārtha Sūtra* 7.1 which prescribes abstinence from violence, and 5.21, which defines the function of souls as rendering service to one another⁵³. The *Ācārāṅga Sūtra*, the earliest texts in Jaina Canon, says "All beings are fond of life, they like survival; life is dear to all"⁵⁴. The same moral advice is also found in the Buddhist text *Dhammapada*: "all tremble when faced with punishment; life is dear to all. Seeing others as ourselves, do not strike, do not cause another to strike"⁵⁵ ("*sabbedañassatasanti sabbemaccunobhāyanti/ attānamupamamkatvānahaneyanaghātaye*" *Dhammapada*, chapter-10, *DaGabhāga*, Verse. 129). The *Ācārāṅga Sūtra* further declares: "all breathing, all existing, all living, all sentient creatures should not be killed, nor driven away. This is the discipline which is pure, eternal, and inalterable and declared by the enlightened ones who have comprehended the nature of the world"⁵⁶. The *Ācārāṅga Sūtra*'s approach to the interrelationship of living beings is very much like that of the Upaniṣads, which also emphasize the interconnectedness of life.

In fine, we may remember the words of Nathmal Tatia⁵⁷, according to whom, the foundations of international understanding and world peace consists in open-mindedness, restraining of the aggressive urge (*ahimsā*) and inhibition of the possessive instinct (*aparigraha*). The conditions of society in the present-day world demand that either we adopt such a catholic outlook of morality or else we perish. We are in the midst of a life where hatred, injustice and intolerance reign supreme. A new orientation of values would be necessary for us to destroy the inverted values and then 'rebuild to our heart's desire. 'What we need today, is love and sympathy and not prejudice and pomp. We need understanding and a sense of fellowship between the peoples of the world'⁵⁸. We will then learn to love our neighbors as ourselves " and we can still cherish the hope when power becomes ashamed to occupy its throne ' and, when the morning comes cleansing the bloodstained steps of the nation "⁵⁹. We

shall be called upon to bring the spirit of morality to sweeten the purity of human destiny. The Jaina theory of morality stands for, according to T. K. Tukol, 'harmony of apparently conflicting doctrines by systematic reconciliation'⁶⁰. It engenders toleration and avoids conflicts. The Great Jaina *ācāryya Umāsvāti* in his monumental work *Tattvārtha Sūtra*⁶¹, rightly advocate the main theme of Jaina dharma in a word that the function of the human beings is to help each other: *Parasparopagraho Jivānām*.

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